

COVERAGE OF PARLIAMENTARY ISSUE IN TURKEY BY FOREIGN AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the issue of coverage of the issue of parliamentarism in Turkestan in the foreign press, its interests and reasons, considering it from different angles, the reasons that distinguish it from the views on this issue in Soviet times, the general conclusions of its authors on this issue, the studies of Turkish historians on this issue, the reasons for the close attention of Turkish historians to this question.

The works of historians who have conducted research on the problem can be divided into three groups according to the geographical principle: 1) researches carried out by Russian, Tatar and Azerbaijani historians in the period after the fall of the Soviet era; 2) works created by Turkish historians; 3) research conducted by historians of other countries (Kazakh, Turkmen, etc.).

In the years after the collapse of the Soviet state, the researches on the problem are distinguished by their impartiality from party and class, the same as the original reality and their wide scope. In particular, D. Seidzade, L. Yamayeva, D. Usmanova, F. Aleskerov, L. G. Protasov, I. K. Kiryanov, A. Kravchenko, T. Kotyukova, P. Multatuli, S. Darchiyeva, D. Khidiraliev, A. Khabutdinov and others [1, 7, 8, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19, 22, 23, 26, 27, 34]. These authors mainly focus their research on political changes and the beginning of parliamentary activity in Russia at the beginning of the 20th century, the participation of Muslim representatives in the Russian State Duma, the All-Russian Constituent Assembly, the holding, calling and fate of elections to it, political views among Muslim peoples. devoted to issues such as development. In particular, L. G. Protasov looked at the issue from a completely new point of view in his research. He avoided the traditional view of the Constituent Assembly and focused more on analysis. In his opinion, the main reason for the defeat of the Constituent Assembly in Russia is the absence of a political elite in this country [20. 11]. Although the researches of the above-mentioned authors discuss the State Duma, the holding of elections to it, and the participation of Muslim deputies in it, there is almost no information about how the

elections were held in Turkestan, and the participation of local representatives in the parliament. For example, T. Kotyukova in her work is limited to providing general information on parliamentary elections in the country, participation of representatives of the country in the Duma [11. 41-45, 60-65, 80-85]. Although authors such as D. Seidzade, L. Yamayeva, and D. Usmanova focused on the activities of Muslim deputies in their works, they also limited themselves to giving general opinions about the elections held in Turkestan and the activities of deputies. At the same time, various authors published articles on this topic [2, 6, 9, 24, 25, 28, 37].

The scientific research carried out by Russian researchers: A. Khabutdinov, D. Gilmutdinov, A. Smetanin, A. Mokeev and others about the State Duma, factions and their activities and the influence of the political events that took place in Russia in 1917-1918 on the political life of local peoples information is given in studies [5, 12, 23, 29, 30, 32], as well as in the materials of a number of scientific and practical conferences [18, 21]. For example, A. Khabutdinov showed the reasons for the beginning of the movement for autonomy among the Muslim nations, the direction, the stages of development on the example of the Russian Tatars [30. 3, 15, 17, 19, 21, 22-27]. Although the authors focus on the activities of Muslim MPs and various factions in their research, they have almost no information on the activities of Turkestan MPs.

Turkish historians have also conducted research on the beginning of the struggle for autonomy in Turkestan, the history of the parliamentary movement in the country. There are reasons for this, of course. First, it can be explained by the fact that representatives of national freedom fighters who were forced to go abroad as a result of the establishment of Soviet power in the country later settled in the territory of the Republic of Turkey, and secondly, it can be explained by the great interest in the history of Turkestan among Turkish historians.

Studies on the political realities of 1917-1918 in Turkestan, the history of the struggle for independence occupy an important place in Turkish historiography. Regarding this issue, the works created by them can be divided into two groups: the first group is about the roots of parliamentarianism in the Turkic peoples, and the second group is directly about the history of the struggle for autonomy in Turkestan in the first decades of the 20th century.

In the studies of the first group, together with the history of the Turkic peoples, the "congresses" that played an important role in the political life of the states, their emergence, convening procedures, discussed issues, the procedure for solving them, the different names of the congresses in history, the name of the representative and other information. given data [44. 256-260, 45. 246-251, 50].

The second group of literature provides information about the activities of the Muslim Bureau in the IV State Duma, the political processes that took place in Turkestan in 1917 [35, 38, 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 46, 47, 48. 15- 19, 49, 55, 56].

At the end of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century, a series of works about Turkestan Autonomy began to be published one after another in Turkey. These works provide interesting information about the activities of the Constituent Assembly, which is considered a component of the Autonomy. For example, in the work consisting of a collection of articles on the history of Turkestan compiled by Temur Khojaogli, there is information

about the formation of ideas about parliamentarianism in the country and about the Autonomy of Turkestan [40,53].

After the termination of Turkestan Autonomy, 50 members of the Provisional Government and People's Council (National Council) were imprisoned [40. 27]. Some of the members of the government managed to escape. One of them was Mustafa Chokai. First, he goes to Tashkent, then to the Caucasus. From there he went to Europe through Turkey and lived in France and Germany until the end of his life. During his emigration, Mustafa Chokai's books on Turkestan Autonomy and the history of Turkestan were published in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan [15, 16, 54].

In the last years of the Soviet Union's power and in the subsequent period, researchers of a number of foreign countries are conducting research on the history of independence movements in Turkestan. They include Edward Carr, Paul Berne, Colin Martin, Adib Khalid and others [33, 36, 51]. In the research of the English historian Edward Carr, the political events that took place in Turkestan in 1917 were given in the form of a brief review [33. 263-264], only. The next study published about the policy of the Bolshevik government in Turkestan is "Central Asia. "Transition Stages" is a collection, which contains brief information about the work carried out by the Turkestan Autonomous Government and the People's Council [51. 92]. The issue was specifically addressed in the "Kokan Autonomy, 1917-18" section of the collection, written by historian Paul Berne [51. 34-35].

The formation of the national idea in Turkestan, the political events that took place in Russia in 1917, its impact on the country's social and political life, national political organizations, the division between them, and finally the Turkestan Autonomy and the reasons for its defeat, the historian Researched in the works of Adib Khalid [37. 63-78]. His thoughts in this regard are distinguished by their novelty compared to the views formed in Uzbek historiography until today about the democratic organizations of 1917. Because it is the national-political organizations formed in 1917 and the differences between them, political division and its causes (ideological contradictions between the religious fanatics that have been preserved for centuries and young people with new political views)) introduced a new concept.

The reason why most of the works published abroad on the subject were created in the Russian Federation and the Republic of Turkey is that Turkestan was a colony of the Russian Empire, and that many Turkestans sought refuge in the Republic of Turkey during the October coup d'état and the subsequent policy of repression. can be explained by the brotherhood of the people.

References:

1. Алескеров Ф.Т., Кравченко А.С. Распределения влияния фракций в государственных думах Российской империи (1905 – 1917 гг.). – Москва, 2005. – 20 с.
2. Андреев А.А. Организация выборов среди туземного и инородческого населения в первую Государственную Думу // Научный диалог. 2020. №3. – С. 298-316.
3. Baymirza Hayit. Basmacilar. Türkistan Milli Mücadele Tarihi (1917-1934). – Ankara, 1997. – 367 s.

4. Баймирза Hayit. Sovyetlerde Türklüğün ve Islamin Bazi Meseleleri. – Istanbul, 2000. – 336 s.
5. Гильмутдинов Д.Р. Ислам и государство в Средневолжском регионе в 1870-1917 гг. (на материале Казанской губернии). Автор. дис. канд. ист. наук. – Казань. 2005. – 25 с.
6. Дарчиева С.В. Национальные, социально-экономические и политические вопросы в работе Северокавказских депутатов Государственной думы России (1906-1917 гг.). – Тамбов. 2015. № 8 (58). – С. 74-80.
7. Дарчиева С.В. Государственная дума Российской империи и вопросы экономического, политического и культурного развития Северного Кавказа (1906 – 1917 гг.). – Владикавказ, 2015. – 260 с.
8. История деятельности первых государственных дум дореволюционной России: сравнительный анализ традиций правотворчества – Москва, 2013. – 240 с.
9. Камалиева Г.Ф. Мусульманские депутаты III государственной думы России (1907 – 1912): борьба вокруг школьного вопроса // Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. 2012. № 34 (288). История. Выпуск. 53. – С. 62-66.
10. Кирьянов И.К. Российские парламентарии начала XX века: новые политики в новом политическом пространстве. Дисс. док. ист. наука. Пермь, 2009. – 537 с.
11. Котюкова Т.В. Туркестанское направление думской политики России (1905 – 1917 гг.). – Москва, 2008. – 202 с.
12. Мокеев А. Б. Участие социалистических партий в выборах во Всероссийское Учредительное собрание. Автореф. дисс. канд. ист. наук. – Санкт-Петербург, 2010. – 28 с.
13. Мультатули П.В. Император Николай II и мусульмане. – Москва, 2013. – 55 с.
14. Мусульманские депутаты Государственной думы России 1906 – 1917 гг. Сборник документов и материалов // Составитель, автор вступительных статей и примечаний Л. Ямаева. – Уфа: Китап, 1998. – 378 с.
15. Мұстафа Шоқай. Шығармаларының толық жинағы. Екінші том. – Алматы, 2012. – 640 б.